

Harnessing Green Talent Management: Pathways to Enhanced Organizational Performance

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ABSTRACT

Green Talent management is one of the fundamental problems public and private sector companies meet. Green Talent Management in an organization is a business strategy that seeks to develop and retain talented and high potential employees. strategic approach of recruiting, developing, and retaining employees with skills, knowledge, and attitudes that align with environmental sustainability goals. This study's research objective is to create a conceptual framework eco-friendly practice into traditional talent management processes to foster a workforce that supports an organization's sustainability objectives. GTM includes practices such as hiring green companies, offering training on sustainability practices, Talent, talent, Sustainable Recruitment and Selection, Green Training and Development, Green Compensation and Benefits program in retaining talent, Sustainable Performance Management, Organizational Commitment

towards Talent management strategies, Workplace Environment and Culture, Identify and Differentiate Talented Employees for higher productivity, Sustainable Workforce Planning, Succession Planning, Organizational Performance & Culture, Organizational Employer Branding. This study attempts to address the critical gap in the organization. Thus, this research is essential for academia and manger to develop talent management, increase talent visibility, and develop employees to meet the organization's talent needs. The aim is to enhance the organization's overall sustainability performance while also attracting and retaining talent committed to environmental stewardship.

Keywords: Green Talent Management, Talent Practices, Employees, Organization, strategy & commitment.

INTRODUCTION

Green talent management strategies are designed to align human resource practices with environmental sustainability goals, aiming to enhance both organizational performance and environmental responsibility. "Developing Talent (Management) is cheaper than buying a Talent. "Building a successful green talent management strategy is the key to success. Recruiting and hiring the right people will lead to an increase in talent image. Identifying talent needs, assessing existing talent, and developing employees to meet talent needs is the Green Talent Management Process flow achievement. Focusing on employee engagement and retention plan followed by implementing a succession planning process will motivate the employee to contribute more to the organization. Designing a high-performance culture will create a strong HR and business partnership. Talent management has two implications. First, the extent of empirical and theoretical work may be underestimated. Secondly, it may be more difficult for reflective practitioners. It is suggested that combining Human Capital Management and Talent Management is a good step. (Collings, Scullion, & Vaiman, 2015). Talent Management has a considerable influence on employee engagement and employee creativity. Furthermore, the results visible that employee engagement mediates related to employee creativity and talent management. (Jehangir, M., & Khan, A. 2018). The talent management dimensions are attraction, sourcing and recruitment, talent reviews, deployment and transitioning, performance management, growth and development, engagement and retention, rewarding and recognizing the activities accordingly to be carried out as per each dimension specified (Van Zyl, E.S., Mathafena, R.B., & Ras, J., 2017).

Talent

For the past 15-20 years, Human Resources (HR) has focused on "talent" that has conquered the profession. The success (from any war) does not come from talent but the organization. The key capabilities of the organization are what the organization is known for and good at. To build sustainable success that leads to victory, the HR professionals deliver talent and organization at an equal level. Human resources bring similar precision to the organization as they have talent and leadership; they will add even more worth to their organization. HR enters the industry game by ensuring talent through creating organization, and HR wins the industry game. The war for talent will be changed into victories through

Organization (Ulrich, 2015). Talent is a mixture of three components: abilities, interpersonal characteristics, and performance. The fourth component of the talent model is Environmental influence (Van Arensbergen, M. T. P., 2015). The study tested the relationship of the variables between Job engagement (JE), Job Flexibility (JF), and Job diversification (JD), leading to the intention to leave the workplace by employees. The analysis also tested the independent variables (JE, JF and JD) towards the dependent variable of employees' intention to leave the workplace. The results showed no relationship between (JE, JF, and JD) and employees' intention to leave the workplace. Through these findings, the organization helps develop the appropriate retention program and eventually help the organization save operational cost. For any organization retaining talented employees is an ongoing issue, and there are several types of expenses associated when employees resign or leave the organization. The primary and core factor in motivating them will help attract and retain employees. (Harjan Singh and Kumar Tarofder, 2020).

Talent Review

How does talent management influence the organization's performance & strategic orientation? Talent Review and Talent development are the most vital part of the organization. The Human Resource Manager and the middle & top managers should hunt for the Top Talents in their departments to successfully implement the process. Good Talent management always creates a place for the correct number of people at the right place at the right time with the right skill sets. Massive, diversified leadership and managerial competency programs include communication skills, service orientation, the capability to interact with customers & suppliers and perform under challenging conditions, and helpfulness to innovation (Latukha, 2016). Having highly talented employees in the organization means high productivity and cost savings. Talent hunger exists in the marketplace, and retaining highly qualified employees is complex. The younger generations frequently change jobs if they are unsatisfied with the current organization. To retain and develop talented employees, the organization should focus not only on the Salary & Benefits but also on the Age, Work Environment, Succession planning, Job security, satisfaction & Flexibility, organization commitment, etc. These factors are the key factors affecting the talent management in the Organization (Rani, 2014).

Talent Management among Gen Y has obtained critical enthusiasm for the organization. Gen Y is called us "Out-of-the-box" thinkers. The gyrosopic management approach alters the planning and coaching for a new gathering of chiefs and can strengthen coaches and mentors (Ismail, 2018). Fifty-six (56) representatives participated via in-depth interviewing as the finding comprised a typology consisting of Four distinct Talent Management types. 1. Humanistic Type means "developing every employee's talent" 2. Competitive type means "identifying a few talented" 3. Elitist

type means "recruiting the most talented among the talents" 4. Entrepreneurial type means "giving talents opportunity to prove themselves" (Bolander, Werr, and Asplund, 2017).

Sustainable Recruitment and Selection

Eco-Friendly Job Descriptions: Include environmental responsibilities in job roles to attract candidates who are passionate about sustainability. The Green Employer Branding promotes the organization's commitment to sustainability to attract talent with similar values. By using the Digital Recruitment - Use online platforms to reduce the carbon footprint associated with traditional recruitment processes. HR due diligence, which includes Background verification, is the key critical duty of HR, starting from identification of candidate, verification of resume, and a face-to-face interview with identified talented pool candidates. This process shall not be left out with the external consultants, while this shall be a core job of HR personnel to prove and give the proper feedback to Top-management. HR Due diligence includes Talent Identification, HRIS Data, Talent Review Data, Appraisal Review Data, and Face-to-Face review Data are key processes (Holland, 2019). In this paper, the author used the method of Biomimicry, which is nothing but taking inspiration, especially from honeybees & ants, by assessing the recruitment process & HCM domain. Considering that to attract suitable talented candidates, we can use the new hires & employees' "what they say about the organization and work culture" blogs can be created and posted on the Job Posting page. It will attract the external candidates to perform better during the interview & hiring process. The new hires and employees can also be eligible to get "Referral Bonus/payouts." Hence this will be in deed a "Win" for the Candidate "Win" for employees, and a "Win" for Organization (Mittapally, N., Baggaraju, A., Swamy, M. K., 2021). Make environmental

responsibilities and qualifications part of every job role. This paper largely focuses upon the various Green Human Resource Practices pursued by the organizations all over the world and, explains the simplified meaning of GHRM. The correlations between these concepts are illustrated in Figure 1. (Ahmad, 2015).

Figure-1. Mediating and moderating mechanisms between signals about CES (Corporate Environmental Sustainability) and applicant attraction outcomes

Green Recruitment and selection by Ahmed 2015

Green Training and development

Environmental Awareness Programs, trains employees in sustainability practices and how their roles impact the environment. Green Skills Development provides training in areas like energy efficiency, waste reduction, and sustainable resource management. Leadership Development equip leaders with the skills to drive green initiatives and create a culture of sustainability. The study investigated ways to succeed in green career management and talent management of the employees. The employee's insights and experiences of using training and development activities are to support career management and talent development in their organization. Data were collected and analyzed to understand how career management and talent

development aspects were explained by training and development within the work setting. There are significant effects of the training occurrence, which needs assessment on career and talent management effectiveness. Apart from that, there are also significant effects on career-focused job rotation practices, induction, provision of mentors on talent development, and career development effectiveness. There is a complementary effect on career management and talent management, along with career- focused training programs and development (Ngirande, Musara, 2016). Growing realization that economic sustainability is intertwined with environmental sustainable development. Recent changes in the global environment have led companies to realize that by exclusively focusing on maximization of shareholder financial returns, the long term economic viability of their firms is threatened. (Bauer, T.N., Erdogan, B. and Taylor, S.M., 2012)

Green Compensation and Benefits program in retaining talent

Eco-Friendly Perks offer benefits like subsidies for public transportation, incentives for carpooling, or rewards for cycling to work. Sustainable Benefits Packages include health and wellness programs focused on eco-friendly practices, such as organic food options or yoga sessions in natural settings. The organization should have a talent retention strategy to prove talented employees to stay. Various practices like empowerment, employee engagement, competitive Compensation and benefits, and career development opportunities will increase the organization's high brand value. A good organization shall have are training strategy and maintain a success rate even for the employee who joined on the first day onwards. An organization having good compensation and benefits program for retaining the talented employee will be much more effective (Kumar Bhattacharyya, 2015)

Figure-2. Types of Compensation

The Management pays attention to the following aspects: First, In line with the current situation and employee's expectations, the factors influencing employee's Job satisfaction should identify properly. Second, the training content shall be rationalized by concentrating on strengthening administrators' creativity and problem-solving skills. Finally, job satisfaction should be essential for developing employees' potential and talent. The administrators need to understand employees' needs, provide material and ethical support in building employees' capabilities, and suggest unconventional ways to improve employees' well- being in the workplace (Ismail and Razak, 2016).

Sustainable Performance Management

Green KPIs Integrate sustainability metrics into performance appraisals, rewarding employees for their contributions to environmental goals. Eco-Innovation Incentives:* Encourage and reward innovative ideas that promote sustainability within the organization. Outstanding leadership encourages the workforce to learn on the job, speak up with ideas and suggestions for change, and have more effective and resistant teams in the face of unpredicted situations. Knowing that you have a leader focused on learning and not just on performance outcomes. It's also key

for them to be intentional about communicating this regularly to the workforce, as it can make all the difference in building a more resilient team. For example, when a subordinate makes a job error, "Well done, you have to learn from the error as experience, rather than scolding them for making a mistake, and it makes a big difference"(Brykman and King 2021). The study was conducted with the company's high potential employees and senior executives. Using assessment tools in the high-development companies has earned their reputation very well. These results were shared with participants, managers, and HR about how organizations evaluate leadership potential. The following elements are assessed: Transparency, high potential labels, Shelf-life of assessments, talent distributions, access to results, attitudes toward assessments, and performance impact. The shelf life of this survey is valid for 2-to 3 years (Church, Rotolo, Ginther, and Levine, 2015). Figure 2 shows the seven hindrances and concluded 'lack of clarity in the career ladder' was found to be the most significant barricade. There is a significant need to analyze workforce sustainability issues by engaging an integrated TISM-DEMATEL approach. It is very shocking that many organizations are ignorant of why employees

are leaving and why do they stay?

Figure-2. Integrated TISM-DEMATEL based model

Organizational Commitment towards Talent management strategies

This article aims to evaluate organizations' approach in the Czech Republic toward the extent of Talent Management and employee training & development. As a result, only 11.5% of organizations have a talent management strategy, 54.8% do not implement talent management, and the sad thing is that around 46.5% of organizations that do not implement talent management do not find it essential. Also, there is the incorporation of Talent Management activities implemented in the organization, and interlinking the Talent management concepts with Organization strategy is a problem (Adéla Fajčíková 2016). Create employee groups focused on sustainability initiatives, encouraging participation in environmental projects. Organize competitions or challenges that promote eco-friendly behavior, such as reducing energy usage or waste. There is a positive linkage between Talent management and organizational commitment. In addition, the study reported an intermediary position on employee engagement among Talent Management activities and organization commitment. (Badshah Hussain, Naveed Iqbal, Muhammad Waseem, Naveed Farooq, Azhar Khan, 2021). The human resource policies and practices are perceived as self-worth, cost of loss, and need to reciprocate based on the affective, continuance, and normative commitments. It shows the relationship between the HRM and the commitment of an organization (see Figure-3).

Figure-3. Association Between HR Policies and Practices with Organizational Commitment

Green Workspaces designs office spaces to minimize energy usage and waste, using sustainable materials and promoting natural light. The organization should focus on identifying the importance of talent management position to attract and retain managers. TM elements significantly impact the organization's performance, providing a better basis for ordering and implementation. The organization must be attractive by offering flexible hours and work-from-home options for highly talented employees. Remote Work Options to reduce commuting by offering flexible work arrangements, such as remote work or telecommuting. Instead of waiting for the annual performance to come in place to provide the employee's feedback, reasonably frequent feedback will help managers and employees the betterment. Keeping employees comfortable at their workplace will repeatedly increase productivity. All the working stations should have a good lighting facility, with room to move freely. Also, it is crucial to avoid employees working from high noise areas as this may distract their work easily. Also, ensure to have the ergonomic way working style. This type of working environment will ensure to retain the best performance in them (Santhosh Kumar, 2013). Some companies choose to apply green criteria when choosing candidates while others do not. In any case, communicating a company's environmental values and direction is worth practicing during Green Recruitment & Selection (GRS). The strength of this effect is guided by five moderators (pro-environmental attitude, socio- environmental consciousness, desire to have a significant impact through one's work, environmental-related standard registration, job seeker's expertise). [Pham, D.D.T.](#) and [Paillé, P.](#) (2020)

Identify and Differentiate Talented Employee for higher productivity

Effective Talent Management is the key to organizational success and increased productivity which will also attract and sustain the top talent in the organization. It is essential that the right skills & highly talented stick with the organization for the long term. Talent Management should be integrated with all aspects of the Human Resource Management function. Effective Talent Management ensures to acquisition and retains highly talented in the organization for successful production(Chidiebere, 2015). Strategies ought to encompass improving the employee value proposition. Ensure to keep away from supply and demand in talent management systems. This mismatch shall cause employee turnover, layoffs, restructuring, or undersupply of talented employees where the critical position could not be filled. Both of these may have a terrible effect on the organization, affecting Talent Management Strategies. The Talent Strategy have to now no longer forget about the talent pool as they have shown aspiration to build a long-term relationship with the employers and ought to have a future source of potential. In order to retain the talent organization must consider employee value proposition. Current HR techniques need to construct to build Flexibility in HR management applications like benefits and professional / career paths(Seopa, Wöcke, Leeds, 2015). Sustainable Workforce Planning

Green Job Rotation Rotate employees through roles that focus on sustainability, allowing them to develop a broader understanding of green practices. Organizations should embrace succession planning management with the HR/Talent Management Team. Only a sustainable knowledge-based leadership model can build a new form of transdisciplinary harmonious–procreant way to achieve real sustainability. Succession planning passed

through five stages of evolution from blooming to maturity, i.e.,

1. No succession planning
2. Replacement planning
3. Traditional succession planning
4. Integrated succession management, and
5. Transparent talent mobility.

In this research, the author found that short-term and long-term strategies are important to keep talented employees and sustain their organization. The organization provides monetary benefits to their talented & skilled employees for their performance, considered "Short Term Strategies. "Employees are more interested in the growth of their organization because the organization provides a sense of Job security; as there is growth in the organization, there are very few chances of it cutting down the workforce. Companies make the employees think they are the organization's most valuable asset. While the long run, companies expect emotional commitment from their employees by providing them with wide-ranging training, valuing employees, and mentoring and coaching programs (Jyoti Sharma,2015).

Succession Planning

Organizations react differently to the challenge of selecting the right leader. Without a transparent and tested succession planning management process, organizations face great risks, resulting in bankruptcy(Florin Talpoş, Pop, Văduva, and Kovács, 2017). Long-Term Resource Planning shall align workforce planning with sustainability goals, ensuring that talent needs are met without compromising environmental objectives. In Pharma Industry, retaining the High& potential talents is always complicated because the succession plan was unsuccessful. The

succession plan will be effective if the TMS (Talent Management Strategy) is successful. Moreover, the right talent identification and good development strategies lead to talent retention and successful succession planning (Jindal, Shaikh, 2020).

Organizational Performance & Culture

This study is aimed to check how the organization's culture affects talent management implementation. Apart from the career management issues, the study's main finding was that organizational culture is one-factor affecting talent management (Hannah Orwa, Jane Njeri, 2017). Enhanced Reputation being recognized as a green organization can improve brand image and attract customers and talent. Cost Savings sustainable practices can lead to cost reductions through energy savings, waste reduction, and improved efficiency. Increased Employee Satisfaction: Employees who value sustainability may feel more engaged and motivated working for a green-conscious organization. Innovation and Growth focusing on sustainability can drive innovation, opening up new markets and opportunities. Implementing these strategies not only contributes to environmental sustainability but also enhances organizational performance by fostering innovation, reducing costs, and improving employee engagement.

One of the factors that affect talent management is Organization culture. One of the processes in talent management is the important role played by the organization's culture. Talent management is crucial for the organization in the current scenario. It isn't easy to retain talented employees. An organization's core values and belief system depend on the organizational culture. In developing the organization's culture, the organization's leaders play a vital role. The types of culture like bureaucratic, clan, entrepreneurial, and market will influence the talent management practices in the

organization. The organizational culture is often at the bottom of the list by the organization's leader. Employees prefer an organization with a positive culture. Organizations are doing various programs to retain talented employees. (Mahajan, 2019).

Figure-4. Model of the relationship between human resource management practices and organizational performance
Authors: Ejovwokeoghene, Yewande, Oluseye & Joseph

Organizational Employer Branding

Organizational Employer branding will help or solve shortage of skilled workforce. In the earlier stage, the applicant has to prove the employer. Still, now due to a shortage of skilled workforce, employers have to convince the potential candidate in a tight labor market. In Employer Branding, employers project themselves as "How do we become an attractive employer by the external presentation of our company" (Trost, 2020). "How an organization clutches the world's leading technology and composes unique technology to overcome the challenges in TA. As there is an increase in technology & new media impact, the candidates need to improve the talents and apply more. Social media impacts the talent branding & attraction." how is the link between strategic HR management (SHRM) and business strategy ([Walford-Wright](#) and [Scott-Jackson](#), 2018).

CONCLUSION

An organization's green talent management targets recruitment, training and development, performance reviews, and Compensation to ensure a good Green Talent Management System. These components of Human Resources contribute to the success of the organization's performance. In this study, the author

identifies the Green talent management strategies components. Some of them are Compensation and benefits in retaining talent, Sustainable Recruitment and Selection, Green Training and Development, Green Compensation and Benefits program in retaining talent, Sustainable Performance Management, Organizational Commitment towards Talent management strategies, Workplace Environment and Culture, Identify and Differentiate Talented Employees for higher productivity, Sustainable Workforce Planning, Succession Planning, Organizational Performance & Culture, Organizational Employer Branding. Thus the organization attracts highly skilled employees but finds it difficult to retain. Thus, applying effective Green Talent Management proves a suggestion for employee development and refining the performance of each employee. Therefore, the research is helpful to the academic world and manager level in the organization to develop talent management, increase talent image and develop employees to meet talent needs in the organization.

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